

Effectiveness of spaced breathing on progress of labour and its selected outcomes among mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals in the city

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Childbirth is a life-transforming, intense event for a woman and her family. Even though a variety of non-pharmacological techniques are readily available to alleviate the distress of women in labour, the majority of women are unaware of their benefits. The objective of the study was to explore the impact of a simple non-pharmacological technique, i.e., spaced breathing exercises, on the progress of labour and maternal outcomes among mothers.

Objectives:

To assess the effect of spaced breathing on the progress of labour and its selected outcomes among mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals.

Methods:

A quantitative quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group pretest–posttest design was adopted to evaluate the effectiveness of spaced breathing on the progress of labour and selected maternal and neonatal outcomes. The study was conducted in selected hospitals of the city over a period of 28 days. A total of 60 pregnant mothers in the latent phase of labour were selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique and assigned to experimental and control groups. The experimental group received spaced breathing intervention for 5–10 minutes during the first stage of labour, while the control group received routine care. Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire for demographic variables, a self-structured checklist to assess progress of labour using partograph parameters, a tool to assess maternal labour outcomes, and standardised tools for neonatal outcomes, including APGAR score and anthropometric measurements.

Results:

The study findings revealed that spaced breathing was effective in improving labour and neonatal outcomes. Mothers in the experimental group showed significantly better progress of labour ($z = 4.9, p < 0.05$). Labour outcomes were more favourable, with lower mean outcome scores in the experimental group ($z = 10.4, p < 0.05$), indicating smoother and less complicated labour. Neonatal outcomes were also significantly improved. Newborns had higher APGAR scores at 1 minute ($z = 12.3, p < 0.05$) and 5 minutes ($z = 5.2, p < 0.05$), along with better anthropometric measurements ($z = 6.5, p < 0.05$).

Conclusion:

The results confirm that spaced breathing is a statistically significant, simple, and non-invasive intervention that enhances labour progress, improves maternal outcomes, and promotes better neonatal well-being.

Keywords: Spaced Breathing, Progress of Labour, Labour pain, demographic variables.

INTRODUCTION

Prolonged labour intensifies labour pain, and failure to address labour pain may lead to abnormal labour and augment the usage of operative interventions. Prolonged labour is common among women, resulting in maternal morbidity, increased caesarean section (CS) rates, and postpartum complications. It may bring forth negative birth experiences that may increase the preference for CS. There is a dearth of evidence concerning the effectiveness of breathing exercises on the duration of labour.¹ Spaced breathing during labour is a conscious technique that focuses on slow, deep breaths. Also known as the Lamaze method, it aims to help individuals feel relaxed and in control during childbirth.

Labour pain is considered one of the most severe forms of pain experienced by women. Excessive pain during labour can stimulate fear, anxiety, and stress, leading to increased catecholamine release. High catecholamine levels can inhibit uterine contractility, prolong labour, and decrease placental perfusion (Lederman, 2017). Prolonged labour is associated with maternal exhaustion, increased operative interventions, postpartum haemorrhage, fetal distress, and reduced maternal satisfaction with the birthing experience (World Health Organisation, 2020). Therefore, methods that reduce maternal stress and support effective contraction patterns are essential for ensuring safe labour progression.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Breathing is one of the simple, cost-effective non-pharmacological techniques that connect the mind and the body. A combination of controlled breathing and conscious relaxation are power-packed tool for labour. Breathing distracts the focus away from pain and enables the mother-to-be to give birth awake and aware. It also enables the woman to control her response to labour and adjust her breathing levels as labour progresses.

Given the importance of maternal comfort, the need to avoid unnecessary medical interventions, and the increasing emphasis on promoting positive childbirth experiences, it becomes essential to evaluate simple, affordable, and effective techniques like spaced breathing. Understanding its impact on labour progress, mode of delivery, maternal satisfaction, and neonatal outcomes will help strengthen labour care protocols and empower healthcare professionals in supporting mothers more effectively.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Understanding the efficacy of spaced breathing techniques is crucial for providing optimal care to labouring mothers. If these techniques are found to be effective, healthcare providers can incorporate them into childbirth education programs and labour support strategies to enhance the birthing experience for women. Pain management during labour is a significant concern for many women. If spaced breathing techniques are shown to be effective in reducing pain

perception and anxiety, they could serve as a valuable non-pharmacological option for pain relief, potentially reducing the need for medical interventions such as epidurals or analgesics. The impact of labour techniques on maternal outcomes such as satisfaction with childbirth experience, duration of labour, rates of interventions (e.g., caesarean sections, assisted deliveries), and postpartum recovery is important to assess. Understanding how spaced breathing techniques influence these outcomes can help to optimise maternal care and improve birth outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group pretest–posttest design was adopted to evaluate the effectiveness of spaced breathing on the progress of labour and selected maternal and neonatal outcomes. The study was conducted in selected hospitals of the city over a period of 28 days. A total of 60 pregnant mothers in the latent phase of labour were selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique and assigned to experimental and control groups. The experimental group received spaced breathing intervention for 5–10 minutes during the first stage of labour, while the control group received routine care. Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire for demographic variables, a self-structured checklist to assess progress of labour using partograph parameters, a tool to assess maternal labour outcomes, and standardised tools for neonatal outcomes, including APGAR score and anthropometric measurements. Experts established the content validity of the tools, and reliability was ensured using Cohen’s kappa method. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including paired t-tests and chi-square tests.

RESULT

SECTION I

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE

Age - In the experimental group, 43.3% of the mothers has age 18-25 years, 40% of them had age 25-30 years, and 16.7% of them had an age 31-35 years. In the control group, 33.3% of the mothers were aged 18-25 years, 40% of them were aged 25-30 years, and 26.7% of them were aged 31-35 years.

Education - In the experimental group, 20% of them were illiterate, 30% of them had primary education, and 50% of them had secondary education. In the control group, 36.7% of them were illiterate, 30% of them had primary education and 33.3% of them had secondary education.

Occupation - In the experimental group, 83.3% of them were housewives, and 16.7% of them had labour work. In the control group, 63.3% of them were housewives, 10% of them had private job and 26.7% of them had labour work.

Type of family - In the experimental group, 33.3% of them had a joint family and 66.7% of them had a nuclear family. In the control group, 30% of them had a joint family, and 70% of them had a nuclear family.

Gestational Age - In the experimental and control group, 46.7% of them had gestational age 37 weeks- 38+6 weeks, and 53.3% of them had gestational age 39 weeks-40+6 weeks.

Section II

Analysis of data related to the effect of spaced breathing on the progress of labour among the experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals.

Table 1: Effect of spaced breathing on progress of labour among experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals.

n=60

Progress of Labour	Experimental		Control	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Very poor	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Poor	0	0.0%	11	36.7%
Good	0	0.0%	3	10.0%
Very good/optimal	30	100.0%	16	53.3%

n=60

Figure No.1 : Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of the sample according to their progress of labour.

Table 2: Two sample z-test for the comparison of progress of labour among experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals

n=60

Group	Mean	SD	Z	p-value
Experimental	8.0	0.6	4.9	0.000
Control	6.0	2.2		

n=60

Figure No.2: Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of the experimental and control group according to their average progress of labour.

Description: Effect of spaced breathing on progress of labour among the experimental group of mothers admitted in the labour ward of selected hospitals: In the experimental group, all mothers (100%) demonstrated very good/optimal progress of labour. In contrast, in the control group, 36.7% of mothers had poor progress of labour, 10% had good progress, and 53.3% had very good/optimal progress. The mean progress of labour score was higher in the experimental group (mean = 8) compared to the control group (mean = 6). A two-sample z-test revealed a statistically significant difference between the groups ($z = 4.9$, $p < 0.05$), leading to rejection of the null hypothesis. These findings indicate that spaced breathing was significantly effective in improving the progress of labour among mothers admitted to selected hospitals.

Section III - Analysis of data related to the effect of spaced breathing on selected outcomes of labour among the experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals.

Description: Effect of spaced breathing on selected outcomes of labour among the experimental group of mothers admitted in the labour ward of selected hospitals: In the experimental group, 56.7% of the mothers had a normal outcome of labour, and 43.3% of them had a mild outcome of labour. In the control group, 6.7% the mothers had normal outcomes, 13.3% of them had mild outcomes, and 80% of them had moderate outcomes of labour.

Two-sample z-test for the comparison of outcome of labour among experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals: The researcher applied two sample z-test for the comparison of outcome of labour among experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals. The average outcome of the labour score in the experimental group was 4.7, which was 10.4 in the control group. The Z-value for this test was 10.4. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average outcome score in the experimental group was significantly lower than that in the control group. The spaced breathing is significantly effective in improving the outcome of labour among mothers.

Section III - Analysis of data related to the effect of spaced breathing on selected outcomes of labour among the experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals

Description: In the experimental group, 56.7% of the mothers had a normal outcome of labour, and 43.3% of them had a mild outcome of labour. In the control group, 6.7% the mothers had normal outcomes, 13.3% of them had mild outcomes, and 80% of them had moderate outcomes of labour.

The researcher applied two sample z-test for the comparison of the outcome of labour among the experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals. The average outcome of the labour score in the experimental group was 4.7, which was 10.4 in the control group. The Z-value for this test was 10.4. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average outcome score in the experimental group was significantly lower than that in the control group. The spaced breathing is significantly effective in improving the outcome of labour among mothers.

Section IV - Analysis of data related to newborn outcomes in experimental group and control group of mothers.

Description: In the experimental group, all the newborns were in excellent condition at minute 1 and minute 5. All the experimental newborns had normal anthropometric measurements. In the control group, all the newborns had moderately depressed levels at minute 1. At minute 5, 20% of them had moderately depressed, and 80% of them had excellent condition. 26.7% of the experimental newborns had normal anthropometric measurements, and 73.3% of them had abnormal anthropometric measurements.

The researcher applied two sample z-test for the comparison of newborn outcomes among the experimental group of mothers admitted in labour ward of selected hospitals. The average APGAR score at 1 minute in the experimental group was 7.4, which was 5.2 in the control group. The Z-value for this test was 12.3. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average APGAR score at 1 minute in the experimental group was significantly higher than that in the control group. The spaced breathing is significantly effective in improving the APGAR score at 1 minute. The average APGAR score at 5 minutes in the experimental group was 9.2, which was 7.7 in the control group. The Z-value for this test was 5.2. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average APGAR score at 5 minutes in the experimental group was significantly higher than that in the control group. The spaced breathing is significantly effective in improving the APGAR score at 5 minutes.

Average Anthropometric measurement score in the experimental group was 0, which was 1.9 in the control group. The Z-value for this test was 6.5. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis is rejected. The average anthropometric measurement score in the experimental group was significantly lower than that in the control group. The spaced breathing is significantly effective in improving the Anthropometric measurement among the newborns.

DISCUSSION

Quantitative Research, Quasi-experimental, non-equivalent control group pretest- post-test design was used for 60 samples, 30 for the experimental group and 30 for the control group were selected from mothers admitted in the labour ward using the non-probability convenience sampling technique. The data was collected by providing a spaced breathing technique on the progress of labour and its selected outcomes. The data was analysed and interpreted by applying statistical methods. The analysis revealed that spaced breathing had a significant positive effect on the progress and outcomes of labour as well as on neonatal health. Mothers in the experimental group demonstrated optimal progress of labour compared to the control group, with a significantly higher mean progress score. Two-sample z-test analysis confirmed a statistically significant difference between the groups ($z = 4.9, p < 0.05$), leading to rejection of the null hypothesis. Labour outcomes were also more favourable among mothers practising spaced breathing, as indicated by a significantly lower mean outcome score in the experimental group compared to the control group ($z = 10.4, p < 0.05$). Neonatal outcomes further supported the effectiveness of the intervention. Newborns in the experimental group showed significantly higher APGAR scores at both 1 minute ($z = 12.3, p < 0.05$) and 5 minutes ($z = 5.2, p < 0.05$), along with better anthropometric measurements ($z = 6.5, p < 0.05$), as determined by two-sample z-tests. These findings indicate that spaced breathing is an effective, simple, and non-invasive intervention that can be integrated into routine intrapartum care to enhance labour progress, improve maternal outcomes, and promote neonatal well-being.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that spaced breathing is an effective, simple, safe, and non-invasive intervention that significantly improves the progress and outcomes of labour as well as neonatal health. Mothers who practised spaced breathing experienced better labour progress and more favourable labour outcomes compared to those who did not. In addition, newborns of mothers

in the experimental group showed better APGAR scores and normal anthropometric measurements, indicating improved neonatal well-being. The statistical analysis confirmed these findings, leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses and acceptance of the research hypotheses. Therefore, spaced breathing can be recommended as an effective technique to be incorporated into routine intrapartum nursing care to enhance maternal comfort, promote smooth labour, and improve neonatal outcomes.

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